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COP-28 DUBAI SUMMIT, FOSSIL ENERGY EMISSIONS, AND PALM BIOENERGY

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RESUME

COP-28 in Dubai in 2023 demonstrates the strong commitment of the global community in reducing GHG emissions and mitigating global climate change. The development of palm bioenergy (first, second, and third generations) is a concrete solution to reduce the consumption of fossil energy (diesel, petrol, aviation fuel, coal, natural gas), considering that the use of fossil energy is the main source of global GHG emissions. Therefore, the palm oil industry and palm bioenergy must be placed as part of climate change mitigation programs at the local, national and global levels.

INTRODUCTION

The United Nations Climate Change Conference (UNFCCC), more commonly known as the Conference of Parties (COP), is an international conference held annually to discuss world issues and commitments in order to prevent climate change and minimize the rise in the Earth's temperature. The COP has been organized since 1995 in Berlin, Germany. This year's event is the 28th session (COP-28) which will take place from 30 November to 12 December 2023 in Dubai, United Arab Emirates (UAE).

Similar to previous COP sessions, the focus of the international conference is to build and renew international commitment to overcome global climate changes which increasingly threaten life on planet Earth. The cause is known and believed to be global warming due to increased emissions of Greenhouse Gases (GHG) into the Earth's atmosphere. ([PASPI 2023](#)).

The largest component of GHG emissions in the Earth's atmosphere is carbon dioxide (CO₂) (Olivier *et al.*, 2022), where these emissions have seen an increase in concentration from 280 ppmv (parts per million volume) in the 1800s to 353 ppmv in 1990 and have continued to rise, reaching 407 ppmv in 2018 (IEA, 2013, 2016, 2019). The United States National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) revealed that the concentration level of CO₂ in the Earth's atmosphere had further increased to 417.6 ppmv in May 2022.

The main source of global GHG emissions (including CO₂ emissions) is also widely known to the public, namely emissions from the use of fossil energy (coal, petroleum and natural gas). Therefore, the global scientific community issued a warning, "stop fossil fuels before it's too late" (IPCC, 2023).

In order to mitigate the increase in GHG emissions, the global community is required to reduce (even stop) the use of fossil energy. However, this poses a challenge, considering that reducing (and stopping) the use of fossil energy also means a decrease in the welfare of the world community. Therefore, there are two solutions that are considered realistic, namely: (1) reabsorbing the already

high concentrations of GHG emissions in the atmosphere, and (2) preventing the increase in the concentration of GHG emissions in the Earth's atmosphere by gradually replacing fossil energy with lower-emission energy.

This article will discuss the contribution of global fossil energy emissions to global GHG emissions. It will also discuss the potential of palm bioenergy as part of the solution, both in reabsorbing GHGs that have already been released into the Earth's atmosphere and as a substitute for fossil energy to reduce GHG emissions.

FOSSIL ENERGY EMISSIONS

The latest study of global GHG emissions (European Commission, 2023; IEA, 2023) revealed that global GHG emissions continue to increase from year to year. Global GHG emissions in 2022 reached approximately 53.8 Gt CO₂ eq. Global GHG emissions in 2022 increased by 1.4 percent compared to the global GHG emissions in 2021, rose by 6.2 percent compared to global GHG emissions in 2020, and increased by 2.3 percent compared to global GHG emissions in 2019 (before the Covid-19 Pandemic).

The top 5 global GHG emitters (Figure 1) are led by China, with emissions of 15.7 Gt CO₂ eq, accounting for 29.2 percent of global GHG emissions. This is followed by the United States with 6 Gt CO₂ eq (11.2 percent), India with 3.9 Gt CO₂ eq (7.3 percent), EU-27 with 3.6 Gt CO₂ eq (6.7 percent), and Russia with 2.6 Gt CO₂ eq (4.8 percent). The emissions from these five countries reached almost 60 percent of global GHG emissions in 2022. These countries have consistently been the Top-5 global GHG emitters since the 1970s ([PASPI, 2023](#)).

Figure 1. Top-5 Global GHG Emitting Countries in 2022 (Source: European Commission, 2023)

The main source of global GHG emissions is fossil energy. Out of the 53.8 Gt CO₂ eq of global GHG emissions in 2022, approximately 76 percent (41.2 Gt CO₂ eq) are emissions originating from fossil energy (European Commission, 2023; IEA, 2023). GHG emissions from fossil energy increased almost 1.5 times from only around 28.1 Gt CO₂ eq in 2000 (Figure 2).

In the period 2000-2022, emissions from coal consumption almost doubled from only 8.9 Gt CO₂ eq to 15.5 Gt CO₂ eq. The contribution of emissions from petroleum (oil) also increased from 9.7 Gt CO₂ eq to 11.2 Gt CO₂ eq. Similarly, natural gas emissions increased from 4.6 Gt CO₂ eq to 7.3 Gt CO₂ eq in the same period. These three fossil energy sources contribute around 82 percent of fossil energy-related GHG emissions.

Figure 2. Contribution of Fossil Energy in Global GHG Emissions in the Period 2000-2022 (Source: IEA, 2023)

The development and composition of global GHG emission sources and GHG emissions from fossil energy have revealed that the total global GHG emissions are still on an increasing trend. The main global source of GHG emissions continues to originate from fossil energy. The three global fossil energy sources, namely coal, fossil oil, and natural gas, remain the major contributors to global GHG emissions. In fact, the contribution of coal emissions has tended to increase significantly over the past 20 years. Likewise, the Top-5 global GHG emitters have not changed.

This condition indicates that international efforts to reduce global GHG emissions, including the adoption of energy mix program, appear to be merely rhetoric. Pressure from developed countries, especially the European Union and the United States, by mobilizing trans-national NGOs on the issue of deforestation, including inhibiting the palm oil industry and other tropical commodities on the grounds of reducing global emissions (PASPI Monitor, [2022a](#); [2022b](#)) is an argument that is misdirected or addresses the wrong problem. The main problem is the increasing and continuing consumption of fossil energy as a source of GHG emissions that cause global warming and global climate change.

Reducing fossil energy consumption should be the main agenda for developed countries in their efforts to reduce GHG emissions. Not the other way around by diverting the issue or addressing the wrong problem, as it does not contribute to solving the main issue, namely reducing global GHG emissions. The global community must focus on finding solutions to the main issue, which is how to reduce fossil energy consumption through substitution with energy sources that have lower emissions and are renewable.

PALM BIOENERGY

To address the increase in global GHG emissions, two solutions are simultaneously needed, namely how to reabsorb GHG emissions that have already been released into the Earth's atmosphere and reduce additional emissions from the Earth to the atmosphere, especially from fossil energy-related emissions. In this regard, the global palm oil industry has the potential to provide both solutions through carbon absorption (carbon sink) and carbon stock storage (biosequestration) (PASPI, 2023; PASPI Monitor, 2023) as well as producing bioenergy as a substitute for fossil energy.

Basically, the palm oil plantation production process is a process of harvesting solar energy and absorbing carbon from the Earth's atmosphere. Thus, oil palm plantations can be viewed as carbon and bioenergy plantations (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Oil Palm Plantations as Carbon and Bioenergy Plantations

The biological production process of oil palm plantations yields three generations of palm bioenergy as joint products. **Firstly**, the First-Generation Palm Bioenergy, which results from the processing of palm oil (Crude Palm Oil/CPO, Palm Kernel Oil/PKO) as the main product of oil palm plantations. This first-generation palm bioenergy has been developed by Indonesia and other countries, namely biodiesel (Fatty Acid Methyl Ester) which is used to substitute fossil diesel. In addition to biodiesel, currently green diesel or palm diesel is also being developed as a substitute for fossil diesel, green gasoline (biopremium/palm gasoline) as a substitute for fossil gasoline, and green avtur (palm bioavtur) as a substitute for fossil aviation fuel. The processing to produce palm green fuel also yields a joint product in the form of biogas which can serve as a substitute for natural gas/LNG.

Secondly, the Second-Generation Palm Bioenergy, which is palm bioenergy produced from the use of oil palm biomass. Apart from producing palm oil (CPO/PKO) as the main product, oil palm plantations also produce palm biomass as a joint product. The biomass includes empty fruit bunches, palm kernel shells, oil palm fiber and shell, oil palm trunks and oil palm fronds. The study by Foo-Yuen Ng *et al.* (2011) showed that each hectare of oil palm plantations can produce biomass of around 16 tons of dry matter per year or around three times greater than the production of CPO and PKO.

Through thermochemical, biological, chemical, and physical conversion technology (Naik *et al.*, 2010), palm biomass can be used to produce various forms of bioenergy such as bioethanol, biocoal, briquettes, biogas and others. Bioethanol can serve as a substitute for or be blended with fossil gasoline while biocoal can serve as a substitute for or be blended with fossil coal.

Thirdly, the Third-Generation Palm Bioenergy, which is palm bioenergy produced from the utilization of CPO mill waste in the form of POME (Palm Oil Mill Effluent). The utilization of POME to produce bioenergy is done by adopting methane capture technology to capture methane gas, resulting in the production of biogas/biomethane. The biogas produced from POME processing has also been widely used as a source of electricity at the local level (in villages around the CPO mills). In addition to biogas production, the application of methane capture technology can also significantly reduce GHG emissions, approximately 66-90 percent (PASPI Monitor, 2023; Nisa and Wijayanti, 2023; Mathews and Ardiyanto, 2015). Another technology that can be used to generate POME-based bioenergy is the use of sludge digester methane capture with algae cultivation technology, resulting in the production of algae biodiesel (Yonas *et al.*, 2012; Nur *et al.*, 2013, 2015; Sukumaran *et al.*, 2014).

Palm bioenergy has at least two advantages as a substitute for/be blended with fossil energy. **First**, palm bioenergy is produced after first absorbing carbon from the Earth's atmosphere (through the photosynthesis process), so it has a relatively low carbon emissions balance compared to fossil energy. Therefore, if palm bioenergy is used to substitute or blend with fossil energy, emission savings will occur. **Second**, palm bioenergy is renewable energy. As long as the sun shines and there is carbon dioxide in the Earth's atmosphere, palm bioenergy will continue to be produced. This is different from fossil energy which is non-renewable and will be depleted.

The substitution or blending of palm bioenergy with fossil energy has been proven to reduce emissions ([PASPI, 2023](#)). The European Commission Joint Research Center (2013) revealed that palm biodiesel produced from CPO mills implementing methane capture technology is able to save emissions of up to 62 percent. When compared with other vegetable oils, the ability of palm biodiesel is also higher than other vegetable biodiesel such as rapeseed biodiesel (45 percent) and soybean biodiesel (40 percent). This is also related to the palm oil production process which generates smaller emissions than alternative vegetable oils (Beyer *et al.*, 2020; Beyer and Rademacher, 2021; [PASPI, 2023](#)).

The research results of Mathews and Ardyanto (2015) have also supported the European Union's findings, where the use of palm biodiesel as a substitute for fossil diesel/diesel can reduce GHG emissions by over 60 percent. The Euro Lex study (2009) also revealed that palm biodiesel can save emissions approximately 62 percent lower compared to the emissions produced from engines using fossil energy.

Indonesia's experience with the mandatory biodiesel program during the period 2015-2021 also indicates that the impact of using palm biodiesel can reduce GHG emissions. The implementation of the mandatory biodiesel (B30) program was able to reduce GHG emissions by 22.3 million tons of CO₂ eq in 2020 ([PASPI, 2023](#)) then continued to increase to 24.4 million tons of CO₂ eq in 2021 and reached 27.8 million tons of CO₂ eq in 2022 (BPDPKS, 2023). This proves that substituting palm bioenergy (biodiesel) for fossil diesel can reduce GHG emissions.

Thus, the global palm bioenergy has the potential to serve as a substitute for or be blended with fossil energy to reduce global GHG emissions. Therefore, the global palm oil industry needs to be positioned as part of efforts to mitigate global climate change, especially in reducing emissions through the substitution of fossil energy with palm bioenergy.

CONCLUSION

The growth of global GHG emissions until 2022 still shows an increasing trend. The top-5 global GHG emitting countries are still consistently held by China, the USA, India, EU-27 and Russia. These five emitting countries contribute to approximately 60 percent of global GHG emissions. Meanwhile, contributors to global GHG emissions still predominantly come from fossil energy with a share of around 76 percent of global GHG emissions.

One solution to reduce global GHG emissions is to reduce fossil energy consumption through substitution with alternative energy sources that are relatively low in emissions and renewable. Palm bioenergy (first, second, and third generations) has the potential to be this solution through its use to substitute or blend with fossil energy that is relatively emission-intensive and non-renewable. Palm bioenergy also has the advantage of being lower in emissions and renewable because it is produced first through the photosynthesis process by absorbing carbon from the Earth's atmosphere.

The substitution of fossil diesel with palm biodiesel and green diesel (palm diesel), fossil gasoline with green gasoline (biopremium/palm gasoline) and palm bioethanol, fossil aviation fuel with green aviation fuel (palm aviation fuel), coal with biocoal, and so on, has the potential to become part of climate change mitigation programs at local, national and global levels. This also indicates that the global palm oil industry needs to be positioned as part of international efforts to reduce global emissions.

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